

FINANCE IS AN ECONOMIC CONCEPT

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ABSTRACT

This article reflects on Accounting Science and accounting. A specialist who has studied accounting understands finance and is able to carry out finance, enterprise or public finance, there will be a cadre that manages to calculate profit in advance. Therefore, it is not for nothing that we call the name of our article business language.

Keywords: *accounting, business, finance, accounting.*

Introduction. Business nifty activity. To conduct business and develop it, you need technologies, raw materials, labor, logistics market and, of course, accounting, and finance for full distribution and control.

Accounting is a continuous book keeping when translated from German, translation from Arabic is an activity that keeps records of durability, receipts and expenditures.

Accounting is an area of knowledge that is of paramount importance in society. Accounting is necessary in a profitable organization. With the help of accounting, the accounting of economic resources such as money, prisons, buildings is carried out.

Accounting is the language of business. At the same time it is a necessary tool for obtaining financial information even in non-profit organizations, that is, in government organizations, hospitals, charitable foundations, mosques, public organizations.

We are talking about the accounting quarter, which accounting mainly uses in the activities of production enterprises.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The Accounting system can be viewed as information. Accounting the purpose of the system is to provide the necessary financial information on production resources and their effective use. This information is processed data. And information is reflected in financial statements. Finance is an economic concept that performs the functions of distribution and control with a monetary unit. Finance is called mustahib in Arabic.

When preparing accounting financial statements, great importance is attached to who this information is intended for. Because, the tasks to be solved from the sides of producers and creditors are different, requiring different approaches and piecemeal study of information. The person who receives the money thinks about how to spend it, while the person who gives the money thinks that he will return his money in time with good. Without thinking, he studies, analyzes information from different sides. Compares, learns. Then he will do the reason not to walk in remorse. Insures. Takes the guarantee. All this will require Accounting information. The basis.

A little information was given in the accounting grid above. A little information was also given in the round of the duties of the accountant.

This specialty is studied by business owners. As soon as you realize that buchglteria accounting is an integral part of modern life today, the language of accounting gradually becomes the language of business people. As described by the American Accountants 'Association, "accounting is the process of valuing, retrieving and processing Economic Information, informed decision – making and information by owners."

This information is mainly reflected in the form of money, having a financial description. That is, the basic unit of measurement is money.

Social infrastructure is a set of networks and enterprises that functionally ensure the normal life of the population. These include housing, its construction, social and cultural facilities, the entire area of Housing and communal services, health systems, education, preschool enterprises and organizations. Enterprises and organizations related to recreation and recreation; retail, catering, services, sports and recreation

areas; passenger transport and utility communications; a system of institutions that provide services of a legal and financial-credit Nature (legal advice, notary offices, savings banks, banks), etc.[Yuldasheva Gulmira Azatovna, & Baltabayeva Malokhat Ortikalievna. (2022). The development of social infrastructure as a factor in managing the innovative development of the region. International JOURNAL of SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 11(05), 65-70. Retrieved from <https://www.gejournal.net/index.php/IJSSIR/article/view/486>].

Accounting is confused with majority accounting. Accounting is a boring, contactless business that is the accounting of economic activity and a mechanical process. How much water flowed. How much electricity was transmitted. How many sheep are grazing, how many workers are there. Pakhtakor scored several goals. How many times was cotton treated with chemicals. Several students come to the first grade this year. How many socks were sold. How many fruits remained in the warehouse, and x.k. Accounting is a broader concept than accounting. Accountants tax and process financial information. They prepare financial statements, carry out audits (audits), develop accounting systems, Tax production and financial activities, solve issues related to taxation.

The accounting process (also called Cycles) will consist of the following groups of functions.

1. To monitor, identify and manage hosts – (a) monitor hosts; (B) separate hosts ‘ economic jixats; (C) manage these hosts in financial form (with sums).
2. For purposes of activity accounting, categorization, and outcome determination, - (A) are accounted for; (B) are categorised; (v)determine the end (outcome).
3. They draw up reports in different options-a) drawing up a financial report; b) anic users (take into account the specific requirements of the users of the report.)

Let’s give examples of calculating finance: comparing the national income and leaders of Uzbekistan in 2020. The national income of Uzbekistan is from the national income of the United States (21286.6 billion. dollar) was 99.7 percent less. China’s national income (\$14,623.8 billion) is 99.6%, Japan’s national income (\$5,156. 4 billion) is 98.9%, and Germany’s national income (\$3,953. 5 billion) is 98.9%.dollar)

by 98.5%, and the UK's national income (\$2,723.2 billion) by 97.8%. The National per capita income in Uzbekistan is 97.3% of the National per capita income (\$64,310.0) in the United States, 96.3% of the National per capita income (\$47,186. 7) in Germany, 95.7% of the National per capita income (\$40,770. 1) in Japan, 95.6% of the National per capita income (\$40,770,13. 7) in the United Kingdom, 95.6% of the Chinese the National per capita income (\$10,160. 2) is 82.8% lower.[Yuldasheva, G. A. (2022). Znachenie innovatsionnogo opita V formirovani povisheniya urovnya doxodnosti naseleniya. Educational sacrifices, 8, 172-185.] These figures will certainly be delivered and collected in the first steps of accounting isobism, and in the Nutshell of this we will have a clear idea. From the data obtained, we will develop plans for the next analysis.

Results

For example, everything will be clear if we give information about washing machines in the instruction of specific numbers: A centralized water use system is being implemented in many rural areas of Uzbekistan. As a result of our research, we learned that the composition of artesian and drainage water is considered harsh for automatic washing machines. The water content coming through the centralized water supply system is soft and convenient as drinking water. As a result, every family tends to use automata.

Firstly, the time spent on washing will be low and productive for any contingent, women and men from the population;

Secondly, automatic washing machines are connected to sewage systems, so that wastewater does not pollute water or soil. A person washing laundry by hand pours used water in a stream or rinses laundry in flowing streams;

Thirdly, when the cost price is reduced to the amount sufficient for purchase by the population, the volume of sales of products increases. For example, in 10 years the number of farms has increased by 66%. This means that in about 10 years, the same increase is expected.¹

¹ Baltabayeva Malokhat Ortiqaliyevna. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY OF ENTERPRISES AND ITS IMPACT ON GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 11(09), 100–104. Retrieved from <https://www.gejournal.net/index.php/IJSSIR/article/view/976>

IN PLACE OF THE CONCLUSION

It is necessary to understand that the information obtained by the account is recorded for later use for certain practical or scientific purposes, or for other events, actions, by obtaining them, the management of the economic activity of an enterprise, organization, institution, which consists in describing the changes that occur in activities in quantities in order to control the activity.

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